

SCHOOL HEADS CONFLICT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND SCHOOL ATMOSPHERE IN LAMBAYONG DISTRICT III

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ABSTRACT

A conflict usually occurs when two or more people communicate. When people think of conflict in simple terms, they think that happens when serious issues and anger are invoked in the communication process. This study examines the school heads' conflict management style practices and school atmosphere in Lambayong District III for the school year 2023-2024. It employed a descriptive-correlational design among ninety-five teachers and school heads. Mean and Pearson–moment correlation coefficient was employed to test the hypothesis. On the extent is the level of practices of the school head in conflict management in terms of, integrating, obliging, dominating, avoiding, and compromising. there were two (2) domains or indicators that were observed to the moderate level, the obliging and avoiding. In the same manner, there were also two (2) domains or indicators which observed to the great level, the dominating and compromising. On extent of the school atmosphere in terms of three (3) domains, social connectedness, positive relationship with school personnel, and intellectual engagement. It further shows that social connectedness and positive relationships with school personnel are identically observed to a great extent. On the other hand, intellectual engagement was the highest among the three, which means that intellectual engagement is observed to the greatest extent. Interestingly it was found that there is no significant relationship exists between conflict management and school atmosphere.

Keywords: *Conflict Management, Practices, School Atmosphere, School Heads, Lambayong District III*

INTRODUCTION

Conflict-handling styles have been analyzed by considering different organizational phenomena such as emotions, personality, or even religions Ayas, T., et. al (2010). This author accorded that there has been an increasing interest in a deeper examination of the impact of culture on conflict-handling styles. Conflict is a recurring decimal in all human relationships, be it in the family, institution, or organization.

More so, the school, like any other modern institution, is not without potential negative features, incompatible behaviors, and conflicts that might be counter-productive and give rise to inefficiency, ineffectiveness, or dysfunctional consequences in the achievement of goals and objectives. The school as a bureaucratic organization with the division of labor, line of authority in terms of teacher-principal, subordinate-super ordinate relationships, rules and regulations, and communication flow - upward, downward, and horizontal is bound to have conflicts.

Teachers' commitment to organization plays a key role in the formation of an integrated effort in the school organization. espoused that school organization needs to build up the necessary efforts to encourage and enable teachers to strive for their strong commitment to the organization. This will enable the school organization to meet future challenges and at the same time maintain teachers' attachment to the organization.

Due to the overstaying of school heads in particular schools, there are problems arise in their conflict management practices in addition due to the change of school heads in a short period, teachers and the school as a whole adjust to the conflict management practices of the school head.

Thus, the research will be conceptualized to find out the conflict management practices of school heads in Lambayong III District and their relation to the school environment for the school year 2023-2024.

Research Questions

This study ascertains the school heads' conflict management practices and school atmosphere in Lambayong District III.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent is the level of practices of the school head in conflict management in terms of;
 - 1.1. Integrating;
 - 1.2 Obliging;
 - 1.3 Dominating;
 - 1.4 Avoiding, and
 - 1.5 Compromising?

2. What is the extent of the school atmosphere in terms of;
 - 2.1 Social Connectedness;
 - 2.2 Positive Relationships with School Personnel, and
 - 2.3 Intellectual Engagement?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the school head's conflict management practices and school atmosphere?

METHODOLOGY

The study uses a descriptive-correlational design. It determines the relationship of the independent variables such as school heads' conflict management styles along with integrating, obliging, dominating, voiding, and compromising, and the school atmosphere as dependent variables and school atmosphere in terms of, Social Connectedness, Positive Relationships with School Personnel, and Intellectual Engagement.

The respondents of the study were the ninety-five (95) school heads together with the teachers in the Municipality of Lambayong District III for the school year 2023-2024.

RESULTS

On the extent is the level of practices of the school head in conflict management in terms of, integrating, obliging, dominating, avoiding, and compromising. there were two (2) domains or indicators that were observed to the moderate level, the obliging and avoiding. In the same manner, there were also two (2) domains or indicators which observed to the great level, the dominating and compromising.

On extent of the school atmosphere in terms of three (3) domains, social connectedness, positive relationship with school personnel, and intellectual engagement. It further shows that social connectedness and positive relationships with school personnel are identically observed to a great extent. On the other hand, intellectual engagement was the highest among the three, which means that intellectual engagement is observed to the greatest extent.

Interestingly it was found that there is no significant relationship exists between conflict management and school atmosphere.

DISCUSSION

On the extent is the level of practices of the school head in conflict management in terms of, Integrating, Obliging, Dominating, Avoiding, and Compromising

Table 1. Level of practices of the school head in conflict management in terms of, Integrating, Obliging, Dominating, Avoiding, and Compromising

INDICATORS	Mean	Description	Interpretation
Integrating	3.23	Partially	Observed to the lesser level
Obliging	3.78	Moderately	Observed to a moderate level
Dominating	4.25	Always	Observed to the greatest level
Avoiding	4.00	Moderately	Observed to a moderate level
Compromising	4.31	Always	Observed to the great level
Over All Mean	3.92	Moderately	Observed to a moderate level

The table exhibits the summary table of school heads' conflict management styles they use in their respective schools if a conflict arises.

The overall mean of 3.92 with a verbal description of moderately which mean it was observed to the moderate level among school heads. More specifically, integrating conflict management style got the lowest mean of 3.23 with a verbal description of partially which interpreted as observed to the lesser level, while obliging conflict management style got the second lowest computed mean of 3.78 which was interpreted as observed to the moderate level among school heads.

Interestingly, compromising got the highest computed mean of 4.31 with a verbal description of Always which mean observed to the great level, followed by domination with a computed mean of 4.25 with a verbal description of Always which is interpreted as Observed to the great level.

Based on the data above therefore comprising is the common use by the school heads to settle conflict in their respective school.

The result of the study conforms to the statement and study of Rahim (2012), that a compromising style may be effectively used to handle strategic and complex issues. In a compromising style, the parties negotiate the strategically important point and let go of the insignificant point. In a few words, a compromising style may be effective in handling immediate conflict but the vital issues should not be sacrificed in the name of compromise. Nevertheless, it is widely used by the school administrators.

On the extent of the school atmosphere in terms of, Social Connectedness, Positive Relationships School Personnel, and Intellectual Engagement

Table 2. Extent of the school atmosphere in terms of, Social Connectedness, Positive Relationships School Personnel, and Intellectual Engagement

INDICATORS	Mean	Description	Interpretation
Social Connectedness	3.90	Often	Observed to a great extent
Positive Relationship with School Personnel	3.99	Often	Observed to a great extent
Intellectual Engagement	4.28	Always	Observed to the greatest extent
School Atmosphere	4.06	Often	Observed to a great extent

The table displays the summary table of the school atmosphere in terms of social connectedness, positive relationship with school personnel, and intellectual engagement with the overall mean of 4.06 which is interpreted as “Observed to a great extent. In particular, intellectual engagement got the highest computed mean of 4.28 with a verbal description of always which means “Observed to the greatest extent, followed by positive relationship with school personnel with a mean of 3.99 and social connectedness with a computed mean of 3.90 both with a verbal description of often which mean “observed to great extent”.

This only concludes that teachers have an evident intellectual engagement among themselves and more on the intellectual conversation for the enhancement of the teaching and learning process.

The result of the study conforms with the study of Fredricks et.al (2014) A study on the relationship between teacher engagement and student engagement suggested that teacher engagement positively influences student engagement, highlighting the significance of teachers' active involvement in fostering student engagement.

On the relationship between conflict management practices and school atmosphere

Table 3. The Relationship Between Conflict Management Practices and School Atmosphere

domains	R-Value	p-value	interpretation
Integrating	.545	.067	Not Significant
Obliging	.493	.104	Not Significant
Dominating	.451	.141	Not Significant
Avoiding	.372	.208	Not Significant
Compromising	.471	.119	Not Significant
Conflict Management (Overall)	.121	.708	Not Significant

Table shows the relationship between the school heads' conflict management practices and the school atmosphere. It can be observed in the table that the p-values of all the conflict management practices domains were all greater than 0.05 level of significance, which means that each of them has no significant relationship with the school atmosphere. Similarly, the overall conflict management practices of the school heads were found to have a p-value of .708 which is greater than 0.05. This implies that the null hypothesis is accepted and therefore concludes that there exists no significant relationship between the school heads' conflict management practices and the school atmosphere.

The result of the study is similar as noted by Adhiambo and Enose (2011), conflict brings stress and discomfort due to the fear of the unknown; hence, it is a depressing and frustrating state of affairs between the parties involved. Conflict affects the smooth running of the teaching and learning process, but, if carefully examined and managed it leads to peaceful coexistence between teachers and their school leaders. However, conflict is inevitable, and in principle, all conflicts cannot be resolved and managed (Ramani & Zhimin, 2010). However, researchers argue that teachers and school leaders should have sufficient knowledge about how conflict occurs, and how they can respond to or manage it to bring positive changes and minimize any negative effects (Olubunmi, 2014)

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

Conflict management of school heads in terms of obliging and avoiding that were observed to a moderate level whereas dominating and compromising were observed to a great level, and intellectual engagement was observed to the greatest extent.

Meanwhile, social connectedness and positive relationships with school personnel are identically observed to a great extent. Finally, there is no significant relationship between conflict management and school atmosphere.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented. The school head may continue its conflict management style which is suited to their school. The teachers may sustain their best school practices to strengthen the school atmosphere. The teachers and school heads may continue or strengthen their harmonious relationship. This study be replicated in a wide scope and may add variables which is not included in this study.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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